

Probing molecular gas conditions in the merging system Arp 142 with CO observations

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ABSTRACT

Merging systems create unique environments that enhance star formation in galaxies. The cause of this enhanced star formation can be due to increased molecular gas or star formation efficiency. Arp 142 ($D \sim 100$ Mpc) consists of an elliptical (NGC 2937) and spiral (NGC 2936) galaxy pair in the early stages of merging. To investigate the physical conditions in the molecular gas and high star formation rate (SFR), we observed Arp 142 using the Submillimeter Array (SMA) at 230 GHz rest frequency to observe the CO (2-1) line. The CO (2-1) data provides new information about higher rotational energy transitions, and we complement our CO (2-1) observations with archival NOEMA CO (1-0) data to probe the excitation conditions of the gas. We generated integrated intensity and line ratio (R_{21}) maps to investigate the excitation of the CO gas. Throughout the system of Arp 142, we then calculated a mean R_{21} value of $0.82^{+0.18}_{-0.16}$, which falls below the calculated mean R_{21} value for a sample of LIRGs with similar properties ($R_{21}^{\text{lit.}} = 1.09 \pm 0.04$). Additionally, using ancillary data from the WISE W3 and GALEX FUV bands, we derived values of the star formation rate surface density of Arp 142 using both IR and UV wavelengths. We then examined the R_{21} value as a function of SFR surface density and found a positive correlation stronger than the one previously found in a study of starburst galaxies with similar properties. Additionally, we examined the relationship between SFR and gas mass for Arp 142 to determine a Kennicutt-Schmidt relation using the CO (2-1) and (1-0) lines respectively. These findings allow us to better contextualize the star formation activity across Arp 142.

1. INTRODUCTION

It has been documented and empirically observed that mergers can trigger enhanced star formation in galaxies (Kennicutt et al. 1987). Thus, star formation can be used as a tool to better understand the effects caused by merging systems as well as the broader processes of galaxy evolution. We thus choose our system, Arp 142 ($M_{\text{mol}} = 10^{10.29 \pm 0.02} M_{\odot}$), to better understand merging galaxy systems and their effects on star formation (Xu et al. 2021). Arp 142's spiral component, with a luminosity distance of 104.0 Mpc, shows a high total SFR of $9.83 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Xu et al. 2021) from the Lisenfeld+2019 survey. Arp 142 consists of the spiral galaxy NGC 2936 interacting with elliptical galaxy NGC 2937. The star formation efficiency (SFE), the star formation rate per unit of gas, varies in different regions of Arp 142 due to tidal disruptions caused by interactions between its spiral and elliptical galaxy components (Xu et al. 2021).

The interactions have led to a star formation rate that is the highest SFR amongst galaxies in spiral-elliptical (S+E) pairs presented in the Lisenfeld 2019 survey, rates that are expected of spiral-spiral (S+S) systems (Lisenfeld et al. 2019). For comparison, the more massive Milky Way Galaxy ($M = 1.2 - 1.9 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$) (Fragione & Loeb 2017) shows much lower SFR ($1.0 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), indicating that Arp 142 contains a highly starforming starburst galaxy.

A quantity that is correlated with star formation is H_2 , which is the most abundant molecule in the Universe (Schmidt 1959; Feldmann 2013). When probing star formation regions in Arp 142, we examine cold, dense regions within the system, making it difficult to directly observe H_2 in our galaxy system. This is because the rotational transition energies of H_2 are relatively high (≈ 500 K), so the excited state of H_2 is generally not found in the cold molecular interstellar medium (ISM) that we observe. Instead, we use the emission lines of CO, which have become a popular tracer of molecular gas in the interstellar medium.

Compared to H_2 , for CO the difference between the energy stored in its excited states is relatively small. For the first energy level, the excitation temperature is 5.5 K, and for the second energy level, the excitation temperature is 11.04 K (Peñaloza et al. 2017). This means the excitation temperatures are relatively low, so CO does not need to be

more than 20 K to be detectable in emission at millimeter wavelengths. This temperature range falls within the range of higher density and lower temperature regions ideal for young star formation (Peñaloza et al. 2017).

One of the primary objectives of this study is to determine the variation of the CO line ratio values (R_{21}) across the galaxy Arp 142. The R_{21} line ratio is particularly useful in probing the variation in rotational excitation conditions across the galaxy due to its sensitivity to density and temperature (Peñaloza et al. 2017). Due to the tidal interaction merging activity occurring in the region, studying the CO line ratios allow us to probe the variation in the rotational excitation conditions across Arp 142. For a survey of normal, star-forming spiral galaxies, a mean R_{21} value of 0.65 was found (den Brok et al. 2021). This value falls below the median R_{21} value of 1.09 calculated for a sample of ultra-luminous infrared galaxies (ULIRGs) that pinpoint gas-rich galaxy mergers (Montoya Arroyave et al. 2023). Thus, by examining the distribution of R_{21} values across Arp 142, we can compare our values to those found in previous literature to probe and contextualize the star formation and excitation conditions of CO gas across the region.

Additionally, we hope to determine a correlation between Arp 142’s resolved R_{21} values with proxy star formation rate surface density values. This will allow us to quantify increasing star formation rates across various regions of activity, to examine if higher excitation conditions correlate with higher rates of star formation. Finally, we hope to examine Arp 142’s Kennicutt-Schmidt (K-S) relation for both the CO (2-1) and (1-0) emission lines. The Kennicutt-Schmidt relation allows us to determine a relationship between star formation rate surface density and molecular gas mass surface density using a power law, suggesting the form $\rho_{SFR} \approx \rho_{gas}^n$, where ρ_{SFR} and ρ_{gas} denote the volume densities of the SFR and the gas respectively (Schmidt 1959). While Schmidt (1959) notes volume densities, throughout this report, we focus on surface density. This is because we measure a column density and effectively only know the extension of the gas in the x and y directions which are limited by our resolution. However, we do not know how far the gas extends in the z direction, so we cannot robustly know the exact volume of gas present. Due to the various regions of SFE throughout Arp 142 due to tidal disruptions, we are interested in examining this surface density SFR and surface density gas mass relation throughout the system to see either a scatter or trend in our data. We also examine this relation at different rotational transitions to probe differing galactic regions, including regions of higher-excited molecular gas with our CO (2-1) line.

2. OBSERVATIONS

We examined rotational energy levels and activity occurring in Arp 142 to better understand its spiral component’s high star formation rate. We observed galaxy Arp 142 using the Submillimeter Array (SMA) Telescope located on Maunakea, Hawaii, as well as archival data obtained from the Northern Extended Millimeter Array Telescope (NOEMA) (Xu et al. 2021) to observe both the CO (2-1) and CO (1-0) lines respectively.

The SMA is comprised of 8 dishes with a 6-meter diameter and is located on the summit of Maunakea, Hawaii at an elevation of around 4000 meters. We observed in the sub-compact configuration at the redshifted frequency of 225 GHz using 2 receivers in dual-mode in each antenna to increase sensitivity. The dual-mode configuration of the SMA allowed for the observation of different polarization states, allowing us to gather more comprehensive electromagnetic radiation information. The beam size in the continuum of CO (2-1) images was $4''$. This overall closer configuration of elements within the interferometer allowed for a lower angular resolution and higher sensitivity to observe our galaxies. For the SMA, our primary beam width/diameter was around $55''$ across, so our field of view of the sky was limited.

As for examining the CO (1-0) line emission, we used ancillary data observed from the Northern Extended Millimeter Array (NOEMA) of the IRAM in the C and D arrays with 10 antennae at 112 GHz (Xu et al. 2021) with a beam size of $4''$. The noise levels for the SMA and NOEMA data can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. CO (2-1) and (1-0) Emission Noise at 8 km s^{-1}

Angular Resolution	CO(2-1) Mean Noise (mK)	CO(1-0) Mean Noise (mK)
$4''$	28.96	4.93
$7.5''$	28.92	4.92

To calculate SFR surface densities, we used ancillary IR and UV intensity data of Arp 142 from WISE and GALEX respectively. To compare this intensity data to our CO observations, we convolved our SMA and NOEMA data to a common resolution of $7.5''$. This resolution cutoff was determined as the lowest resolution to convolve our CO data

down to a common resolution as our ancillary WISE and GALEX data. In Table 2, we describe the differences between the WISE and GALEX bands and their purposes.

Table 2. WISE and GALEX Bands

Telescope/Band	Central Wavelength	Probing
WISE W1	3.4 μm	Warm dust, galaxies, stars, asteroids
WISE W2	4.6 μm	Cooler dust, general infrared emission
WISE W3	12 μm	Warm dust, star formation, mid-infrared
WISE W4	22 μm	Cooler dust, star formation, mid-infrared
GALEX FUV	135 nm to 175 nm	Hot, massive young stars, energetic stellar populations, active star formation
GALEX NUV	175 nm to 280 nm	Hot and cooler stars, younger and older stars, galaxy evolution

3. METHODS

To process the CO (2-1) and (1-0) data from Arp 142, we work with spectral data cubes. We used Common Astronomy Software Applications (CASA) to calibrate, image, and clean the SMA interferometric data. When imaging the data we used a natural weighting function. This modified the sampling function of our interferometer, maximizing point source sensitivity. This was expected, as natural weighting weighs each visibility point by its noise variance. This gave us images with the best sensitivity possible.

From these cleaned and weighted spectral data cubes, we run `PyStructure`, a Python-based script suited to homogenize and combine 2D and 3D astronomical datasets, to help us deal with oversampling in our data. We ran `PyStructure` with a pixel size of half the beam size for our different datasets, minimizing the oversampling to allow Nyquist rate sampling.

We run `PyStructure` at a 4'' resolution, the original resolution of the SMA, to construct a more detailed R_{21} plot. We additionally run a second modification at 7.5'', convolving down the SMA and NOEMA data to a common resolution of our ancillary WISE and GALEX data.

The `PyStructure` code required inputs including the resolution, beam size, and pixel size of the data. Additionally, it took in several inputs, including the CO (2-1) and (1-0) data cubes and Far UV (FUV) and Near UV (NUV) data from GALEX and WISE bands W1, W2, W3, W4.

3.1. Calculating SFR and Gas Mass Surface Densities

The W3 and W4 bands are centered on approximately 12 and 22 μm respectively, which are associated with thermal emission from dust and are often used for observing star formation regions (Wright et al. 2010). The FUV band, at 135 nm, is particularly sensitive to ultraviolet radiation emitted by hot, young stars (Morrissey et al. 2007). Thus, we focus on using these emission bands to proxy star formation rates in Arp 142.

For our 7.5'' `PyStructure` version, we extract integrated intensity values for the CO (2-1) and (1-0) data cubes. From this data, we divide the CO (2-1) integrated intensity by the CO (1-0) integrated intensity values to generate a 7.5'' resolution R_{21} plot with a pixel size of 3.75''. We then calculate the SFR surface density using IR emission proxies from the WISE W3 band by extracting values from the W3 band of WISE using Equation 1 from (Leroy et al. 2019).

$$\frac{\Sigma_{\text{SFR}}}{1M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2}} = (3.77 \times 10^{-3}) \frac{C}{10^{-42.9}} \frac{I_{12\mu\text{m}}}{1\text{MJy sr}^{-1}} \quad (1)$$

where $\log(C) = -42.9$. C calibrates the empirical relationship between SFR and intensity of emission for the W3 band. This equation converts IR intensity values of Arp 142 taken by WISE in the W3 band at 12 μm into SFR surface density values. We thus can explore the existence of a correlation between R_{21} values and star formation rate surface density across Arp 142. We repeat this process additionally with a UV emission proxy:

$$\frac{\Sigma_{\text{SFR}}}{1M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2}} = (1.04 \times 10^{-1}) \frac{C}{10^{-43.35}} \frac{I_{\text{FUV}}}{1\text{MJy sr}^{-1}} \quad (2)$$

where $\log(C) = -43.35$ (Leroy et al. 2019), and C once again calibrates the empirical relationship between SFR and intensity of emission for the FUV band. This equation instead calculates a star formation rate surface density using UV emission. We calculate star formation rate surface density from both IR and UV emission proxies to examine if we see similar trends using the two. The detected UV emission from Arp 142 comes from young stars in the galaxy, whereas the IR emission is re-radiated from interstellar dust in the ISM.

We additionally calculated SFR using both UV and IR intensities using Equation 3 following Yajima et al. (2021) (adopted from Leroy et al. 2008; Casasola et al. 2017):

$$\frac{\Sigma_{\text{SFR}}}{1M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2}} = 1.59(3.2 \times 10^{-3} \frac{I_{22\mu\text{m}}}{\text{MJy sr}^{-1}} + 8.1 \times 10^{-2} \frac{I_{\text{FUV}}}{1\text{MJy sr}^{-1}}) \quad (3)$$

where I_{22} and I_{FUV} are the intensity of the WISE W4 and GALEX FUV bands respectively.

We additionally model our data through a Kennicutt-Schmidt relation similar to those from (Yajima et al. 2021). We plot our calculated SFR surface density values as a function of gas mass surface density. To calculate a gas mass surface density, we use Equations 4 and 5.

$$\Sigma_{\text{H}_2} = \alpha_{\text{CO}_{1-0}} I_{\text{CO}_{1-0}} \quad (4)$$

$$\Sigma_{\text{H}_2} = \frac{\alpha_{\text{CO}_{1-0}}}{R_{21}} I_{\text{CO}_{1-0}} \quad (5)$$

where we choose an α_{CO} value calibrated for the CO(1-0) emission line, I_{CO} is the integrated intensity value for each respective CO line, and R_{21} is the mean R_{21} value for normal star-forming galaxies determined to be 0.65 (den Brok et al. 2021). The α_{CO} value used is a “starburst” α_{CO} value, calibrated from looking at nearby starburst galaxies. We use an α_{CO} value of $1.0 \frac{M_{\odot}}{\text{pc}^2} \frac{\text{K km}}{\text{s}}$ (Bolatto et al. 2013). This value was calibrated for the CO (1-0) integrated intensity line and had to be adjusted when calculating the Kennicutt-Schmidt relation for the CO (2-1) line by dividing the calibration constant by R_{21} . We plot this value as a function of star formation rate surface density to get our Kennicutt-Schmidt Relation.

4. RESULTS

We first obtained our integrated intensity plots of Arp 142 for both the CO (1-0) and CO (2-1) lines respectively at $4''$. These are shown in Figure 1.

We then divide these integrated intensity values to obtain our R_{21} plot as seen in Figure 2. With our R_{21} plot, we used a S/N cutoff of 15 for both CO lines. This high S/N cutoff was necessary due to noise effects dominating the edges of our beam, ensuring that data points with high noise effects were filtered out of our dataset.

When examining the CO (2-1) line ratio throughout the galaxy system Arp 142, the mean and 16th-84th percentile range is $0.82^{+0.18}_{-0.16}$. We further subdivide Arp 142 into two regions– the “beak” and the “arch.” The “beak” describes the region of gravitational interaction between the two galaxies NGC 2936 and NGC 2937, and the “arch” describes the rest of the body of NGC 2936’s spiral component as seen in Figure 3. To regionally examine Arp 142, we used SAOImage DS9 to draw regional masks, referencing Figure 3. This provided a more clear image to draw regional masks around Arp 142 to then apply as a band to a PyStructure modification. When doing so, we calculated a mean value of $0.96^{+0.11}_{-0.11}$ for the merging region of the “beak.” This value was higher than the mean value calculated for the rest of Arp 142’s “arch”, which had a mean value of $0.74^{+0.12}_{-0.11}$. These images can be seen in Figures 4 and 5.

We then used equations 1, 2, and 3 to convert archival W3 IR and GALEX FUV intensity data of Arp 142 into a SFR surface density. As SFR traces the sources that will affect the excitation conditions informing R_{21} , including temperature and density, we compare the SFR surface density and R_{21} to better determine a relationship between the two. To do this we performed a pixel-to-pixel comparison of the SFR surface density and R_{21} value to search for a positive correlation in Figure 7. We report the correlation slopes, Pearson coefficients, and null hypothesis P-values in Table 3. We found that the SFR (IR+UV) showed a significant correlation with a slope of $0.67^{+0.03}_{-0.02}$ and null hypothesis P-value of 1.75×10^{-6} , the SFR (IR) showed a more moderate correlation slope of $0.36^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$ with a null hypothesis P-value of 0.003, and the SFR (UV) showed no statistically significant correlation.

We estimate the uncertainty of the slope by resampling the data with its respective noise. We then fit a linear regression to the resampled data, and our uncertainty and mean values are calculated from the distribution of slope

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Figure 1. Plots of the integrated intensity (moment 0) maps of the CO (2-1) and (1-0) line emission for Arp 142. The integrated intensity is scaled by the color bar shown at the top in units of K km s^{-1} . The contour line represents differing areas of S/N values for the galaxy- the outermost contour demonstrates an area with a S/N value of 5, the second-most contour a S/N value of 10, and the innermost contour with a S/N ratio of 15 for both the CO (2-1) and CO (1-0) line emissions. The gray circle in the lower left represents the beam size of our angular resolution of $4''$. Our grid is half-beam spaced- thus, our demonstrated pixel size is $2''$.

Figure 2. The image to the left is a $4''$ resolution R_{21} plot for Arp 142. R_{21} plot was obtained by taking the integrated intensity values of the CO (2-1) line and dividing it by the integrated intensity of the CO (1-0) line, only including pixels where the S/N of the integrated intensity for both lines is > 15 . The contours show a S/N ratio cutoff of 20, 25, and 30 respectively for the CO (2-1) emission line. From this CO line ratio plot, we were able to calculate a mean R_{21} value of $0.82^{+0.18}_{-0.16}$, a median value of 0.79, and a standard deviation of 0.16. The beam size of $4''$ is once again shown by the gray oval in the bottom left corner. The image to the right is a histogram showing the variance of R_{21} values across the galaxy with a bin size of 0.1. The red and green lines denote the median and mean values respectively, the black line represents the 16th percentile value, and the purple line represents the 84th percentile value.

Figure 3. The image to the left from NASA, ESA, and the Hubble Heritage Team shows the composite HST narrow band emission of the galaxy Arp 142. The continuum image allowed us to clearly view the “beak” and “arch” regions to draw masks subdividing the area. The image to the right shows these “beak” and “arch” regions outlined in the red and green circles respectively. The white circle shows the overall SMA field of view observed for this study.

Figure 4. $4''$ resolution R_{21} plot for the “beak” interacting site within Arp 142 between spiral galaxy NGC 2936 and elliptical galaxy NGC 2937. The pixel size for each point is $2''$, and the plot only includes pixels for the ratio calculation where the S/N of the integrated intensity for both CO emission lines is > 15 . The contours show S/N levels of 20, 25, and 30 for the CO (2-1) emission line respectively and outline the broader shape of Arp 142. From this CO line ratio plot, we were able to calculate a mean “beak” R_{21} value of $0.96^{+0.11}_{-0.11}$ and a standard deviation of 0.11. The beam size of $4''$ is once again shown in the bottom left corner. The image to the right is a histogram showing the variance of R_{21} values across Arp 142’s “beak” with a bin size of 0.1. The red and green lines denote the median and mean values respectively, the black line represents the 16th percentile value, and the purple line represents the 84th percentile value.

Table 3. $\text{Log}_{10}R_{21}$ vs. $\text{Log}_{10} \sum_{\text{SFR}}$ Correlation Slopes and Statistics

Star Formation Proxy	Slope	Slope Standard Deviation	Pearson R Coefficient	Null Hypothesis P-value
IR	$0.36^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	0.015	0.59	0.003
UV	$0.09^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	0.02	0.13	0.55
IR+UV	$0.67^{+0.03}_{-0.02}$	0.02	0.82	1.75×10^{-6}

Figure 5. $4''$ resolution R_{21} plot for the “arch” region of Arp 142. The pixel size for each point is $2''$, and the plot only includes pixels for the ratio calculation where the S/N of the integrated intensity for both CO emission lines is > 15 . The contours show S/N levels of 20, 25, and 30 for the CO(2-1) emission line respectively and outline the broader shape of Arp 142. From this CO line ratio plot, we were able to calculate a mean “arch” R_{21} value of $0.74^{+0.12}_{-0.11}$ and standard deviation of 0.12. The beam size of $''$ is once again shown in the bottom left corner. The image to the right is a histogram showing the variance of R_{21} values across Arp 142’s “arch” with a bin size of 0.1. The red and green lines denote the median and mean values respectively, the black line represents the 16th percentile value, and the purple line represents the 84th percentile value.

Figure 6. Histogram showing the variance of R_{21} values across Arp 142, including the “arch” and “beak” with a bin count of 15. The 3 histograms are non-normalized, each showing their raw frequency count across Arp 142. The blue histogram in the background shows R_{21} values across the entire observed region, the green histogram shows R_{21} values for the “arch,” and the orange histogram shows the R_{21} values for the “beak.” All histograms have an integrated intensity S/N mask for values > 15 . The green dot displays the mean value, $0.82^{+0.18}_{-0.16}$, of R_{21} across all of Arp 142, the black dot represents the mean value of R_{21} across the “arch,” $0.74^{+0.12}_{-0.11}$, and the red dot represents the mean value $0.96^{+0.11}_{-0.11}$ of R_{21} across the “beak.” The extending black lines represent the spread of data between the 16th and 84th percentile values for each respective region.

values for $\log_{10} R_{21}$ vs. $\log_{10} \sum_{\text{SFR}}$ from the individual resampled data. These are shown in Figure 12 located in the Appendix.

We also generate plots displaying the Kennicutt-Schmidt relation between SFR surface density and gas mass surface density using individual sightlines to Arp 142. We thus use Equations 4 and 5 for both the CO (2-1) and CO(1-0) lines respectively. We model our plots in the same style as those from Yajima et al. (2021) as seen in Figure 8.

Figure 7. Plot to the left shows the relation between $\log_{10} R_{21}$ vs. $\log_{10} \sum_{\text{SFR}}^{\text{IR}}$ using $7.5''$ resolution CO line ratio data and $12 \mu\text{m}$ WISE W3 IR intensity data. The $\log_{10} R_{21}$ vs. $\log_{10} \sum_{\text{SFR}}^{\text{UV}}$ plot using ancillary UV data from the GALEX FUV band is shown in the middle plot, and the $\log_{10} R_{21}$ vs. $\log_{10} \sum_{\text{SFR}}^{\text{IR+UV}}$ plot using both ancillary FUV and WISE W4 $22 \mu\text{m}$ IR data is shown to the right. The pixel size of each data point in both plots is $3.75''$ using the same S/N mask as in Figure 2. The error bars represent the calculated $\log_{10} R_{21}$ uncertainty, and the red line displays the line of best fit to the R_{21} vs. SFR surface density data points. The orange line displays the linear regression correlation between R_{21} and SFR for a set of nearby, star-forming main sequence galaxies (Leroy et al. 2022).

We similarly estimate the uncertainties by resampling the data with its respective noise to find the mean slope and standard deviation of the relation, which can be seen in Figure 9 and Table 4. We found no correlation between gas mass surface density and SFR surface density for our S/N mask > 15 for both CO lines. However, when we decreased the S/N mask to > 5 , we found that the data showed a statistically significant trend which we show in Figure 10.

It is difficult to compare these results of our K-S plots to those found in (Yajima et al. 2021), as we used different methods to calculate \sum_{H_2} . Yajima et al. (2021) assumed an R_{21} value of 0.7 to calculate \sum_{H_2} , where we assumed an R_{21} of 0.65 (den Brok et al. 2021). Additionally, we used different methods to calculate \sum_{SFR} , had different sensitivities, and Yajima et al. (2021) had a lower integrated intensity S/N mask of 4.5 compared to our S/N mask of 15. Thus, we instead compare the slopes of our K-S plots for the CO(2-1) and CO(1-0) lines in Figure 10 to each other. The slope of the CO (2-1) line K-S relation with an integrated intensity S/N mask > 5 was $0.67_{-0.00}^{+0.01}$, and the slope of the CO (1-0) line K-S relation with the same mask was $0.66_{-0.00}^{+0.00}$. Thus, we found similar correlation slopes when calculating \sum_{H_2} with the CO(2-1) and (1-0) lines respectively. These results are summarized in Table 5

Table 4. $\log_{10} \sum_{\text{SFR}}^{\text{IR+UV}}$ vs. $\log_{10} \sum_{\text{H}_2}$ Integrated Intensity (S/N=15 Mask) Statistics

CO Emission Line	Slope	Slope Standard Deviation	Pearson R Coefficient	Null Hypothesis P-value
2-1	$0.11_{-0.001}^{+0.01}$	0.0001	0.19	0.4
1-0	$-0.14_{-0.00}^{+0.00}$	2.24×10^{-5}	-0.23	0.30

5. DISCUSSION

When interpreting our results of the R_{21} plot for Arp 142 as seen in Figure 2, we can examine our mean value for the CO line ratio. When comparing our R_{21} mean value of $0.82_{-0.16}^{+0.18}$ to the median value seen in Montoya Arroyave et al. (2023) of 1.09 ± 0.04 , we find that our value is smaller. However, our value is higher than the average R_{21} value of 0.65 for nearby, star-forming spiral galaxies (den Brok et al. 2021) with SFR surface densities of $2.8 - 21 \times 10^{-3} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2}$, \sum_{SFR} lower than those calculated for Arp 142 as shown in Figure 7. Additionally, our mean value was found to be larger than a mean R_{21} of 0.79 ± 0.03 found in a sample of galaxies from Saintonge et al. (2017). When comparing our R_{21} value to those found in these studies, it is important to examine the populations of galaxies surveyed. The ultra-luminous infrared galaxies (ULIRGs) surveyed in Montoya Arroyave et al. (2023) pinpoint gas-rich galaxy mergers undergoing intense starbursts and supermassive black hole accretion. Additionally, the galaxies in this survey have star formation rates higher than the one reported for Arp 142's spiral component of $9.83 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. Out of

Figure 8. Kennicutt-Schmidt (K-S) plots showing the relationship between SFR and molecular gas mass in Arp 142 on a log-log scale with the same S/N mask used in Figure 2. Each pixel represents a pixel size of $3.75''$. The K-S plot on the left plots the hydrogen gas mass surface density values calculated as a function of SFR surface density (UV+IR) using the CO (2-1) emission line, and the plot on the left represents the K-S plot using the (1-0) emission line to calculate this hydrogen gas mass surface density. To calculate hydrogen gas mass surface density using the CO(2-1) line, we had to divide our α_{CO} value by the mean R_{21} found for normal, star-forming galaxies (den Brok et al. 2021). Error bars for the gas mass surface densities are plotted with each data point. When attempting to compare these plots to those found in Yajima et al. (2021), it is important to note the different S/N ratio masks, different approaches to calculating \sum_{H_2} , as well as different sensitivities to our data. This makes it difficult to directly compare our relationship to other relationships found in (Yajima et al. 2021) and other literature values.

Figure 9. Histograms estimating the uncertainty of the relations between SFR Surface Density and gas mass. We estimated the uncertainty of the slope by resampling the data with its respective noise. We then fit a linear regression to the resampled data, and our uncertainty and mean of the slope are calculated from the distribution of slope values for $\log_{10} \sum_{\text{SFR}}$ vs. $\log_{10} \sum_{\text{H}_2}$ from the individual resampled data. The plot to the left shows the histogram of slopes for the Kennicutt-Schmidt relation derived using the CO (2-1) line, and the plot to the right shows the relation derived using the CO (1-0) line. The mean slopes were $0.11^{+0.01}_{-0.001}$ and $-0.14^{+0.00}_{-0.00}$. Low error bars in the CO (1-0) Kennicutt-Schmidt relation are due to the higher sensitivity of the data.

40 surveyed galaxies, only two have SFRs lower than that of Arp 142, with the highest SFR of 590 ± 220 coming from galaxy IRASF224911808. This could help explain the larger value of R_{21} found in Montoya Arroyave et al. (2023). As for the sample of galaxies surveyed in Saintonge et al. (2017), these galaxies are mostly constrained to luminous or nearby galaxies with lower star formation rates compared to Arp 142 ($0.01 - 3.04 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$). Thus, Arp 142's mean R_{21} value falls below those of galaxies with higher SFRs and above those of galaxies with lower SFRs, showing

a correlation between values of high/low SFR and high/low R_{21} . Additionally, we see in Figure 7 that higher values of \sum_{SFR} infer higher values of R_{21} , supporting the finding that ULIRGs would have higher R_{21} values due to their higher SFRs and normal-star forming galaxies or galaxies with lower SFRs would have lower R_{21} values as seen across the literature.

Additionally, when subdividing Arp 142 into separate regions, we see a higher mean R_{21} value of $0.96^{+0.11}_{-0.11}$ in the “beak” region in comparison to the mean R_{21} value of $0.74^{+0.12}_{-0.11}$ throughout the “arch” region of Arp 142. This higher mean value translates to a region of higher CO excitation conditions where the dynamical merging interactions between NGC 2936 and NGC 2937 occur, indicating regions of higher temperature and density. The “beak” R_{21} value found is also closer to the mean R_{21} value reported for a sample of ULIRGs in Montoya Arroyave et al. (2023). We also expect merging to cause brief periods of enhanced star formation (Daddi et al. 2010). Thus, we can see that the CO ratio is indeed sensitive to excitation conditions, mainly an increase in heating caused by bright stars (Peñaloza et al. 2017). We see this through \sum_{SFR} , which traces this increase in heating as the bright stars are located in regions of active star formation (Narayanan & Krumholz 2014). These results are consistent with the positive correlation we find between SFR surface density and R_{21} values in Figure 7, suggesting higher rates of SFR in Arp 142’s beak.

When further examining our SFR vs. R_{21} plots seen in Figure 7, we can see that for the IR and UV+IR proxy of SFR, our regression fit falls above that calculated by Leroy et al. (2022). The positive trend we observe matches the expected correlation of R_{21} and \sum_{SFR} (Narayanan & Krumholz 2014). However, for the case of Arp 142 ($\text{SFR} \approx 9.83 M_{\odot} \pm \text{yr}^{-1}$), the correlation is ≈ 5 times steeper than the correlation empirically determined for nearby star-forming disk galaxies with SFRs between 1 - 5 $M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$ (Leroy et al. 2022), SFRs lower than the overall SFR for Arp 142. A steeper correlation means that the CO emission seems more sensitive in Arp 142 due to changes in the excitation conditions. This could relate to the dynamical state of the gas being different in a merger galaxy in comparison to normal star-forming galaxies.

However, we do not see this trend in our R_{21} vs. $\sum_{\text{SFR}}^{\text{UV}}$ plots as seen in Figure 7. With a Pearson r coefficient and null hypothesis P-value of 0.13 and 0.55 respectively, we can see that there is not a statistically significant correlation between the two. This can be due to several reasons. UV is heavily subjected to extinction in comparison to IR emission due to its absorption by interstellar dust. The UV emission itself traces large, young stars in the galaxy which is why we used it as a proxy for star formation. However, if the young stars are embedded in clouds of dust, the amount of photons detected in the UV has to be corrected by an extinction coefficient. We thus use Equation 3, which uses both UV and IR emission as proxies for star formation, which found the highest correlation slope between SFR surface density and R_{21} values, with a slope of $0.67^{+0.03}_{-0.02}$, as well as a Pearson r coefficient of 0.82 and a null hypothesis P-value of 1.75×10^{-6} . This shows a strong, positive correlation between R_{21} and SFR surface density. Thus, it is necessary to combine both the UV and IR bands, as each on its own do not fully capture the complete picture of SFR in the system.

As for the K-S plots in Figure 8 derived using the CO (2-1) and (1-0) emission, we do not see a statistically significant positive correlation between hydrogen gas mass surface density and SFR surface density. This could be for several reasons: when using Equations 4 and 5 to convert from CO intensity to hydrogen gas mass, we assumed a constant $\alpha_{\text{CO}_{1-0}}$ which may be false. Due to Arp 142’s tidal interactions, the galaxy system has varying SFEs throughout the region which our $\alpha_{\text{CO}_{1-0}}$ may not account for. As the conversion factor is dependent on the physical conditions of the molecular gas, such as temperature, density, and metallicity, if these physical conditions vary spacially, the conversion factor might also vary (Bolatto et al. 2013). Thus, using an $\alpha_{\text{CO}_{1-0}}$ value that takes these variations into account may be necessary to convert from the intensity of CO emission to hydrogen gas mass surface density.

Additionally, Equation 3, our star formation rate surface density equation reported in (Yajima et al. 2021), uses conversion constants derived from a Kroupa initial mass function, which mathematically characterizes the distribution of initial masses for newly formed stars in a stellar population. Although it is a possibility that these conversion constants may not be the most reliable, our tight correlation between R_{21} and SFR, as seen in Figure 7, can most likely rule out this previous analysis.

However, when decreasing the S/N mask of our CO (2-1) and CO (1-0) integrated emission from >15 to >5 , we observe that a major barrier in observing a correlation in our Kennicutt-Schmidt plots is due to our low dynamical gas mass range (\approx dex range of 0.5). Yajima et al. (2021), which observes a correlation between \sum_{H_2} and \sum_{SFR} , observes a dex range of 2. When we decrease our S/N mask to >5 , we find a more, statistically significant positive correlation between SFR surface density and gas mass surface density for the CO (2-1) and CO (1-0) emission lines as seen in Figure 10. We see a slope for the CO (2-1) and CO (1-0) relations with gas mass surface densities of $0.67^{+0.01}_{-0.00}$ and

Figure 10. Kennicutt-Schmidt (K-S) plots showing the relationship between SFR and molecular gas mass in Arp 142 on a log-log scale using S/N cutoff masks of 5 for the individual CO (2-1) AND CO (1-0) integrated intensity emission lines. Each pixel represents a pixel size of $3.75''$. The K-S plot on the left represents the plot generated using the CO (2-1) emission line, and the plot on the right represents the K-S plot using the (1-0) emission line. The K-S plot using the CO(1-0) emission contains more data points due to its better sensitivity in comparison to the CO(2-1) emission (Table 1), as well as its slightly brighter beam. To calculate hydrogen gas mass surface density using the CO(2-1) line, we had to divide our α_{CO} value by the mean R_{21} found for normal, star-forming galaxies (den Brok et al. 2021). Error bars for the CO (2-1) and CO (1-0) lines are plotted with each data point. We do not compare these results to those K-S plots shown in (Yajima et al. 2021), which showed the K-S relation we expected in the ISM of galaxies. This is because our study used different S/N cutoffs, sensitivities, and methods to calculate \sum_{SFR} and \sum_{H_2} . Thus, we chose to compare the slopes of our CO(2-1) and CO (1-0) K-S relations to each other, finding slopes of $0.67_{-0.00}^{+0.01}$ and $0.66_{-0.00}^{+0.00}$ respectively.

$0.66_{-0.00}^{+0.00}$ respectively. We thus see similar K-S relations between both lines. However, it is important to note the lack of physicality of these points at this stage in our research. Correct S/N masks need to be applied to the SFR surface density values, as well as points toward the edge of our spacial map which may be dominated by noise effects. These factors will be taken into account in future studies. Additional statistical information regarding the correlations of our Kennicutt-Schmidt relation for our S/N mask > 5 can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. $\text{Log}_{10} \sum_{\text{SFR}}^{\text{IR}+\text{UV}}$ vs. $\text{Log}_{10} \sum_{\text{H}_2}$ Integrated Intensity (S/N=5 Mask) Statistics

CO Emission Line	Slope	Slope Standard Deviation	Pearson Coefficient	Null Hypothesis P-value
2-1	$0.67_{-0.00}^{+0.01}$	0.001	0.42	0.003
1-0	$0.66_{-0.00}^{+0.00}$	0.001	0.77	3.37×10^{-21}

6. CONCLUSION

Our study of CO emission throughout the starburst galaxy Arp 142 has allowed us to shed light on the star formation activity and its connections to molecular gas occurring within the galaxy. By studying the integrated intensity maps, CO line ratio (R_{21}) maps, SFR vs. R_{21} plots, and K-S plots, we have been able to better quantify the rates of activity occurring in the S+E merger.

Through this process, we have determined a mean R_{21} value of $0.82_{-0.16}^{+0.18}$ across Arp 142's spiral galaxy NGC 2936, with higher R_{21} values ($0.96_{-0.11}^{+0.11}$) located near the onsite of gravitationally interacting and merging. As we expect merging to cause brief periods of enhanced star formation, we can see that the CO line ratio is sensitive to excitation conditions that trace regions of active star formation. Additionally, we calculated a strong, statistically significant, positive correlation between $\text{log}_{10} \sum_{\text{SFR}}^{\text{IR}+\text{UV}}$ and $\text{log}_{10} R_{21}$ for Arp 142 with a slope of $0.67_{-0.02}^{+0.03}$ and a null hypothesis p-value of 1.75×10^{-6} . This allowed us to view an ≈ 5 times stronger correlation between SFR surface density (using IR+UV proxy) and R_{21} than the relation found in Leroy et al. (2022), which mostly surveyed nearby star-forming disk

galaxies with a SFR of $1-5 \odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$. This further provides support for the idea that CO emission seems more sensitive in merging system Arp 142 to changes in the excitation conditions in comparison to normal star-forming galaxies. Finally, we did not find a statistically significant K-S correlation for our S/N mask of 15 for the individual CO(2-1) and (1-0) lines. This is most likely due to a low dynamical gas range of 0.5 dex. However, when we decreased our S/N mask to > 5 , we found a more positive, statistically significant correlation between \sum_{H_2} and $\sum_{\text{SFR}}^{\text{IR+UV}}$. However, further analysis and more sensitive CO(2-1) data are required to validate the physicality of these points.

7. APPENDIX

Figure 11. Histograms estimating the uncertainty of the relations between R_{21} and \sum_{SFR} using different proxies for SFR. Uncertainty was estimated by resampling the data with its respective noise. We then fit a linear regression to the resampled data, and our uncertainty and mean of the slope are calculated from the distribution of slope values for $\log_{10} R_{21}$ vs. $\log_{10} \sum_{\text{SFR}}$ from the individual resampled data. The plot to the left shows the histogram of slopes for the IR SFR proxy, the central plot displays the histogram of slopes for the UV proxy, and the rightmost plot displays the histogram of slopes for the IR+UV proxy. The mean slopes were $0.36^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$, $0.09^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$, and $0.68^{+0.02}_{-0.03}$ respectively

Figure 12. Histogram to the right estimating the uncertainty of the relation between R_{21} and SFR Surface Density using the IR+UV proxy from Equation 3. The black dot represents the mean slope value comparing R_{21} and SFR surface density using the IR+UV proxy, the red dot represents the mean slope when calculating SFR surface density using the IR proxy, and the green dot shows the mean slope using the UV proxy. The extending black lines show their respective 16th and 84th percentile values which are aligned with the dashed orange, purple, and green lines FOR IR+UV, IR, and UV proxies respectively. We can thus see the correlation between R_{21} and SFR Surface Density become stronger as we use the IR+UV proxy for SFR Surface Density.

8. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to acknowledge Dr. Jakob den Brok, Dr. Qizhou Zhang, and the SMA Collaboration at the Center for Astrophysics for their direct assistance throughout this project. Additionally, I would like to thank Professor Chen for facilitating our weekly discussions for Astronomy 98, as well as my classmates.

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